

Sustain Sahel

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Main Authors: Carla Pinho, Lisa Haller (FiBL Europe)

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Author(s)	Carla Pinho, Lisa Haller (FiBL Europe), Contributions: Christian Grovermann, Gian Nicolay (FiBL), Patrice Djamen (AFAAS), Eva Schlecht (UNI KASSEL)
Editor	Harun Cicek (FiBL)
Approved by	Harun Cicek (FiBL)
REA Project Officer	Alina KOZACENKO

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I. Executive summary

This report pertains to Task I.3 “Data Management” and describes the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the **SustainSAHEL** project, funded by the **Horizon 2020** Programme under Grant Agreement number **861974**.

This initial version of the DMP defines the **data management life cycle and general policy and approach to data management in SustainSAHEL**. It follows the structure of the Horizon 2020 DMP template. It reflects the status of the data that is collected, processed or generated, includes the methodology and standards to be used, whether and how this data will be shared and/or made open, and how it will be curated and preserved. It includes for example topics like data and meta-data collection, handling of personal data, publication and deposition of open data, the data repository infrastructure (Collaborative workspace platform) and compliance to the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE).

The DMP is a living document, which **will evolve during the lifespan of the project, particularly** whenever significant changes arise such as dataset updates or changes in Consortium policies.

2. Data summary

SustainSAHEL data will include:

- i. Survey data through PRA (participatory rural appraisal) providing an overview of the main features of the designated sites in the Sahel area (biophysical, human, economic, financial, socio-cultural, symbolic, farm data), identify the most relevant actors related to the key value chains. (WP2),
- ii. Data used to conduct socio-economic assessments, constraints, models to the adoption of CLS integrated systems through farmer`s household surveys (WP2-3), livestock keepers` survey data (WP6)
- iii. Scientific data generated from adoptable designed CLS systems affecting and impacting soil ecology, livestock husbandry, landscape and human needs (WP4-6),
- iv. Geo-statistical and scenario modelling data of CLS systems (WP7), scenario modelling data of livestock and manure management systems (WP6)
- v. Personal data such as contact information of project partners stakeholders, research participants, innovation platforms (IP) etc. for policy briefs, recommendations, working and final papers on roadmaps (WP2-3, 8)

2.1 Participatory rural appraisal (PRA) and survey data (WP2-WP3), livestock keepers` survey data (WP6)

WP2-3 will rely on comprehensive survey data through a participatory rural appraisal (PRA) approach on the main features of designated Sahel sites (biophysical, human, economic, financial, socio-cultural, symbolic, farm data) as well as in farmer`s household surveys to asses socio-economic constraints, models to the adoption of CLS integrated systems. WP6 may require additional survey data to identify livestock holdings that participate in trials with selected shrub-foliage containing diets.

More specifically the data set and the purpose of the data collection of data generation in relation with the objectives of the project used is described in Table 1

#	Data type	Description & purpose	Utility
WP2 Task 1	Qualitative and quantitative survey data	<p>Description Face-to-face interview/survey data with paper-based noted responses to open questions. . The notes are analyzed in country-based PRA teams and integrated with tertiary information (statistics, grey literature etc.) into the site-specific mapping (in the form of the Site report).</p> <p>Purpose Mapping the sites (socio-ecological, incl. history and trends) in order to have the base for research and capacity building activities.</p>	base for planning site-operations (IP, experiments, identifying drivers, policy recommendations)
WP2 Task 2	Longitudinal qualitative and quantitative survey data	<p>Description Based on surveys, literature review and focus group discussions to collect data on socio-economic constraints farmers</p>	To be analyzed for comparisons among countries and findings to

		<p>(including youth and women) and value chain actors are facing in harnessing the potential of CSL integration and their perceived related consequences on their farming practices and performances. When necessary, translation of the data collection tool and the interviews / discussions into local languages will be used.</p> <p>Purpose To propose options for considering socio-economic constraints in the co-design processes of PRSP systems</p>	<p>be published in a scientific publication.</p>
In order WP2 Task 3	Workshops/FFS data	<p>Description Diagrams of mental models made on paper will be generated in group workshops of farmers in each country. These diagrams will be recorded by photo and digitized. Demographic information about participating farmers will be collected through a paper survey format.</p> <p>Purpose To determine how farmers conceptualize soil management in practice and to determine barriers to uptake of CSL principles and discuss potential options for solutions</p>	<p>To be analyzed for comparisons among countries and findings to be published in a scientific publication.</p>
WP2 Task 4	Qualitative survey data	<p>Description Through the use of the capacity assessment grid, target interviews and group discussions, data on existing technical and functional skills at individual and organizational levels of agricultural advisory services</p> <p>Purpose To determine capacity development needs of extension organisations and their staff fort the efficient promotion of CSL-based farming practices</p>	
WP3	Quantitative survey data	<p>Description WP3 foresees farm-level collection of socio-economic data in Niakhar, Senegal and in Kolikouro, Mali. Structured questionnaires with closed questions will be administered to a representative sample of farm households, including farms that participate in project capacity development activities (intervention group) and farms that do not participate (control group). One survey will take place before capacity development</p>	<p>To be synthesized and used in reporting and publications on agroforestry adoption and on the impact of project interventions.</p>

		<p>interventions start (baseline) and a follow-up survey will be conducted after activities have been completed (endline). Comparison of key outcome variables across time and groups will allow for the quantification of project impacts. Outcome variables for which data will be collected include attitude towards, awareness of and adoption of improved shrub integration. Besides these outcome variables, data will be collected on farm and farmer characteristics (size, age, education, etc.)</p> <p>Purpose To determine farmers' attitudes, awareness and uptake of agroforestry and to systematically evaluate the impact of project interventions, generating sound policy-relevant evidence on impacts and scaling potential.</p>	
WP6 Task 2	Quantitative and qualitative survey data	<p>Description Face-to-face survey data with recorded responses to both closed and open questions related to livestock production and feeding management (CSPPro software). Survey recordings conducted in local language will be directly translated into English, CSPPro survey data will be exported as csv files for data analysis.</p> <p>Purpose To identify and characterize livestock holdings that participate in trials with selected shrub-foliage containing diets (animal species and health status, livestock production goals and intensity).</p>	To be analyzed to identify livestock holdings in each country that will be willing to implement designed foliage feeding and manuring strategies.

2.2 Scientific data generated from adoptable designed CLS systems impacting on soil ecology, livestock husbandry, landscape and human needs (WP4-7)

SustainSAHEL will generate agronomic and environmental data from adoptable designed CLS systems impacting on soil ecology, livestock husbandry, landscape modelling to be used throughout the project. Experimental data, statistical analysis, data of meta-analysis will be described in scientific publications according to rigorous scientific standards for transparency, reproducibility and conciseness vs. completeness.

#	Data type	Description & purpose	Utility
WP6 Task 2+3	Scientific data, quantitative and qualitative interview data	<p>Description Data on feed intake, animal health status, fecal quantity and quality and enteric methane emissions will be continuously</p>	To be analyzed for comparison of different types

		<p>collected on-farm, in addition to data from foliage manuring and mulching trials (soil quality, plant development and biomass quantity and quality, nutrient leaching) that will be implemented on-station and on-farm; furthermore, socio-economic data related to the implementation of selected foliage feeding and manuring strategies will be assessed in face-to-face interviews with the participating crop-livestock farmers. Data will be coded and entered into Microsoft Excel for statistical analysis.</p> <p>Purpose</p> <p>To obtain input data to calibrate the LIVSIM and HEAPSIM model for livestock and manure management (Task 6.4).</p>	<p>of livestock holdings; findings will be published in several scientific papers and serve to establish a central livestock and crop database for modelling.</p>
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2.3 Geo-statistical and scenario modelling data of CLS systems (WP7), scenario modelling data of livestock and manure management systems (WP6)

SustainSAHEL will conduct analysis of landscapes using state of the art remote sensing technology and techniques producing geo-statistical and scenario modelling data of CLS systems.

The NUANCES modelling approach (LIVSIM, HEAPSIM) and the LUCIA model will be used to evaluate the selected foliage feeding and manuring strategies to identify optimal site-specific CSL systems.

#	Data type	Description & purpose	Utility
WP6 Task 4	Modelling data	<p>Description</p> <p>LIVSIM, HEAPSIM and LUCIA models will be calibrated and used to evaluate selected and alternative foliage feeding and manuring strategies.</p> <p>Purpose</p> <p>To identify optimal site-specific CSL systems.</p>	<p>To derive practical recommendations for optimal site-specific CSL systems; to develop hands-on application tools for practitioners; modelling results will be published in several scientific papers.</p>

2.4 Personal data such as contact information of project partners stakeholders, research participants, innovation platforms (IP) etc. for policy briefs, recommendations, working and final papers on roadmaps (WPI-3, 6, 8)

Data collected in WP8 “Capacity development, networking and dissemination”, WPI “Project Management”, and to those activities in WP2-3 within the rural participatory appraisal and Innovation platform meetings, pertains mainly to the collection of personal data. This refers specifically to the user account and profile information that is needed for project internal administrative purposes as well as external dissemination (WPI), community building and exploitation activities (WP8). This encompasses also personal data of SustainSAHEL partner personnel for operating the project’s mailing lists, collaboration platform (SharePoint-data archiving platform) and personal data of external users as addressed of the project’s dissemination activities (newsletters, event invitations, etc.) other activities related to surveys, on-farm and on-station trials (WP6), meetings (attendees lists) of the Innovation Platforms in WP2 and 3.

The datasets comprise information like name, organization, email address, role, etc. that is for the most part collected from the respective users through direct input when registering at the respective websites and to the surveys and questionnaires conducted within the WP. For more information regarding this point, refer to 3.4 and D9.1 on informed consent and D9.2 on protection of personal data.

3. Data management policy

SustainSAHEL general data management policy that is presented has been developed in accordance with Horizon 2020 FAIR principles, open data requirements and implementation guidelines. It applies mainly to new results that are produced in SustainSAHEL and that are to be made available by the project consortium as open source, open science and open data.

3.1 Open data

All open data, publications and open source software produced in SustainSAHEL (open SustainSAHEL results) will be identifiable and locatable by means of a persistent Uniform Resource Locator (URI). If possible, open SustainSAHEL results will be assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) in order to make content easily and uniquely citable. Thereby, SUSTAINSAHEL relies on external services, since DOIs can only be assigned by DOI registrants through a DOI registration agency (see https://www.doi.org/doi_handbook/8_Registration_Agencies.html).

Open SustainSAHEL results that are deposited in the SUSTAINSAHEL default Open Access repository will be assigned a DOI automatically.

Open SustainSAHEL results that are deposited in institutional repositories, repositories of scientific publishers or other data and research repositories will be at least identifiable by a persistent URI. If the institution is a DOI registrant that has an agreement with a DOI registration agency, a DOI will be assigned, too.

Whether scientific publications will be assigned a unique identifier like DOI, Publisher Item Identifier (PII), International Standard Serial Number (ISSN), etc. depends on the open access strategy (green or gold) chosen by the editors and thus also on the respective scientific publisher and the chosen research repository.

3.2 Metadata

Metadata for describing the data that is collected and generated by the SustainSAHEL project is not only needed for facilitating open access to the data, it may also be needed, e.g. when searching or accessing data. There are many different meta-data standards for many different types of data and it may not be possible to find one that fits all purposes. Therefore, a pragmatic and feasible approach is to agree on a common and minimal catalogue metadata schema for those datasets that are published in public catalogues and data repositories and to use data-type specific schema extensions, if necessary.

Default Catalogue Metadata schema for open data generated by the project

For SustainSAHEL, the following deposition metadata fields are mandatory:

- title

Title of the deposition.

- description

Abstract or description for deposition.

- files

Deposition files identifiers, filenames, size of the files in bytes and MD5 checksum of files

- upload_type

Type of the deposition from a controlled vocabulary (publication, dataset, software, ...).

- publication_date

Date of publication in ISO8601 format (YYYY-MM-DD).

- creators

The creators/authors of the deposition.

- license

Open license from controlled vocabulary "Open Definition Licenses Service"

- doi

Digital Object Identifier assigned by the DOI registrant

- keywords

Free form keywords for this deposition.

- related_identifiers

Persistent identifiers of related publications, datasets and software

- grants

List donors

3.3 Data accessibility (e.g. by deposition in a repository) & interoperability

SustainSAHEL open results will be made accessible according to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020.

Open Data

All open results (data, software, scientific publications) of the project will be openly accessible at an appropriate Open Access repository as soon as possible. Specifically, research data needed to validate the results in the scientific publications will be deposited in a data repository at the same time as a publication. Non-public research data will be archived at the repository using a restricted access option.

Scientific Publications

Publications are to be accessible, and to comply with Open Access regulations. Prior to publication of results derived from the project, the grantees shall ensure that consent is obtained by all the relevant parties involved in their creation. They regulate the authorship as follows:

Any publication that is coming out of this project will have several authors, who must all be able to give full information on its content and conclusions. The first author is generally the one, who has done the research and who elaborates the first draft of the manuscript. The second author has most closely collaborated with the first author, who helped during the elaboration phase and who has full overview on the original data and the content of the paper. The last author is either the academic professor supervising the student, or the project coordinator and the team leaders, who conceptualized the idea or outlined the study or organized the project, but this is optional. All other authors appear in alphabetical order. The

corresponding author has a long-standing position. The authorship of an upcoming manuscript has to be decided at the beginning of the study or at the early phase of writing the manuscript and needs to be agreed by the Steering committee.

Providing open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications can be ensured either by publishing in green or gold open access journals with or without author processing fees. Any scientific publications from SustainSAHEL and the related bibliographic metadata must be made available as open access and announced on the project website as well as in the OpenAIRE portal (<https://www.OpenAIRE.eu/>) and the R&I Participant Portal (<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants>). To automate the process of reporting scientific publications and related research data in OpenAIRE, the publication should be deposited in an OpenAIRE-compliant repository, either by the authors of the publication (green open access) or by a scientific publisher (gold open access). While additional forms of disseminating open access papers, including academic social network sites such as ResearchGate (<https://www.researchgate.net/>) are possible, an electronic copy of the publication has to be deposited in suitable open access repository in the first place.

If the chosen repository is not fully OpenAIRE compliant, the publications or data must be linked at <https://www.openaire.eu/participate/claim> with the respective funding agency (European Commission). Green open access journals or gold open access journals without author processing fees should be preferred for disseminating SustainSAHEL scientific publications. Nevertheless, the journal's visibility and prestige (translated in the Impact Factor) of the journal, together with the speed of publication, should be considered when choosing a journal for publication of a manuscript. According to the EC recommendation, authors of the publication are encouraged to retain their copyright and grant adequate licences to publishers.

Green open access (self-archiving)

Green open access or self-archiving means that the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript is archived by the researcher itself in an online repository, in most cases after its publication in the journal. The journal must grant the researcher the permission to self-archive the final peer-reviewed article, at the latest, 12 months after publication.

Gold open access (open access publishing)

Gold open access means that the publication is available by the scientific publisher as open access. Some journals require an author-processing fee for publishing open access. Author-publishing fees for gold open access journals can be reimbursed within the project period and budget. Some publishers allow the researcher to deposit a copy of the article in a repository, sometimes with an embargo period.

3.4 Processing of personal data and data protection

SustainSAHEL takes the handling of personal data seriously and is committed to ensure data protection and privacy. The processing of personal data (i.e. data collection, handling and destruction) will be done in compliance with national and, where applicable, EU legislation including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, REGULATION (EU) 2016/679).

SustainSAHEL will process personal data in line with the following principles:

- **Lawfulness:** When processing personal data, the personal rights of the person concerned (data subject) must be respected. Personal data must be collected and processed in a lawful manner (cf. Art. 6 DSGVO; in the case of SustainSAHEL particularly. consent of the person(s) concerned,

contract execution, pre-contractual measure, fulfilment of a legal obligation, legitimate interest of the person responsible).

- Transparency: The data subject must be informed about the handling of his or her data. In principle, personal data must be collected from the data subject him/herself. When collecting the data, the data subject must at least be able to recognize or be informed accordingly about (1) the identity of the responsible party, (2) the purpose of the data processing and, if applicable, (3) the transfer to third parties.
- Purpose limitation: Personal data may only be processed for the purposes that were determined before the data was collected.
- Data minimisation: The collection of personal data is limited to what is directly relevant and necessary to accomplish a specified purpose. The data will only be retained for as long as is necessary to fulfil that purpose.
- Accuracy: Personal data will be stored correctly, completely and - if necessary - up to date. Appropriate measures will be taken to ensure that inapplicable, incomplete or outdated data is deleted, corrected, supplemented or updated.
- Storage limitation: Data will only be stored as long as it is necessary to fulfil the purpose.
- Integrity and confidentiality (security).
- Accountability: The partners of SustainSAHEL are responsible for the lawful handling of personal data. The Work Package leaders supervise the data processing in their WP and its compliance with privacy rules.

SustainSAHEL processes different categories of personal data, such as:

- Master data (names, addresses)
- Contact data (e-mail address, telephone number etc.)
- Content data (text entries, photos, videos)
- Usage data (interests, website visited, purchasing behaviour, access times)
- Meta/communication data (equipment IDs, IP addresses, location data)
- Contract data (e.g. contractual relationship, product or contractual interests, payment information, customer category, credit rating data)
- Business contact details

Data subjects will be informed, among other things, about the purpose of the collection, the categories of data concerned, any disclosure to third parties and their rights (including the right to complain to the responsible data protection authority DPA). **Where applicable, data subjects will be asked to give their informed consent, before the processing of their data starts, e.g. research participants. WP leaders are responsible for the collection and storage of the consent forms.**

The project partners will implement appropriate technical and organisational measures (TOMs) to protect personal data against unauthorised access, unlawful processing or disclosure, as well as against loss, falsification or destruction.

Wherever possible, personal data will be anonymized or pseudonymized. Pseudonymized data means that it can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the need for additional information (cf. allocation of identifiers for survey data). The additional information (reference tables) will be stored separately and access limited to WP leaders. Anonymized data means that the person is not identifiable by any means. Data protection rules for personal data are, therefore, not applicable to this data.

The research results of this project will be published in an aggregated and anonymized form, unless the data subject gave clear consent. The datasets, which in general do not exceed a size of 100k per user account, are stored in an internal restricted repository under the regime of data protection and privacy and will not be made openly available. More information on the respective procedures is given in D9.1 and D9.2.

4. Data storage and archiving

The data generated, or used by the project and not covered by data protection is managed and shared using the secure internet-based “SustainSAHEL Collaborative Workspace Platform”. This allows data to be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). During the project lifetime, access to data is restricted to project partners to help ensure full exploitation.

The collaborative platform was created in order to i) efficiently valorise data in each Work Package (WP) and between various WP by cross-analysis, ii) use efficiently experimental data for modelling and iii) to save data and associated metadata for future use after the project.

Particular attention is paid to the non-disclosure of data that may compromise justified interests of the institutions and of data with exploitation potential. Data not requiring protection is discoverable, accessible, assessable, interoperable and useable beyond their original purpose.

4.1 Curation and preservation

SustainSAHEL data generated (except proprietary background or foreground IP) is a data archive facility (“Data Resource Centre”) provided by FiBL by the administrative and scientific coordination (WPI). The archiving facility will continue to be hosted by FiBL beyond the SustainSAHEL project for future analysis by the scientific community and the organic sector, on FiBL’s own resources. The size of the data to be stored might range between 10 GB and 1TB.

4.2 Exploitation

The Steering Committee of the project identifies project results with exploitation potential or commercial value or results that are costly and difficult to replicate. The Steering Committee assesses the best options for exploiting these results (e.g. opt for disclosure and publication of results or protection through patent or other forms of IPR), consulting patent attorneys, IP specialist agents and officers at the partners’ Knowledge Transfer Departments if required. During the general meetings, a special session on IP issues will be scheduled to enable open discussions and joint decisions on the best strategies for managing and exploiting the project results. Hence, protection of the interests of all the involved parties are ensured. This will enable the exploitation strategy by all parties to be reviewed regularly and to make sure any relevant result is on route for exploitation (directly by the partners or indirectly by third parties) with convenient terms and conditions for all project partners. Decisions relating to data management needed between meetings will be approved through correspondence.

5. Organisation and functioning of data archiving

FiBL has the responsibility of designing the SustainSAHEL Collaborative workspace and managing its functioning (described in details in Deliverable D1.2). This workspace will be partly used to save data acquired during the SustainSAHEL project, and also to capitalise on “acquired data” of partners who would agree to have them shared at the benefit of the project (specified as background in the “backgrounds” annex of the Consortium Agreement).

The coordinator of SustainSAHEL, as WPI leader, is supervising the full process and helps each WP leader to ensure the efficient use of the SustainSAHEL Collaborative Workspace Platform, and for solving eventual difficulties to obtain data from partners.

The WP leader organize the experimental work in the WPs by ensuring that common protocols are implemented (common or specific protocols as decided by the partners under the responsibility of the WP leader). Each Research Team located in several countries and institutes carries out the experimental work in the WPs. The SustainSAHEL Collaborative Workspace Platform allows to bring together in the same support and the same format the various and heterogeneous experimental data collected. The WP leaders organise the design of Template Files for collecting data. The Research Teams collaborate with the WP leader by providing data and by depositing the labelled files and cross-referencing in the directory of the S SustainSAHEL Database. The SustainSAHEL Collaborative Workspace Platform also comprises a common description and labelling scheme to allow for clear identification of experiment ID, owner of data, study directors, experimental designs, codes and data.

The SustainSAHEL experimental database is composed of various files (templates completed by each Research team) including data and metadata required. The SustainSAHEL experimental database is a specific directory hosted on the SustainSAHEL Collaborative Platform. Each partner has access to the SustainSAHEL Collaborative Platform. This main directory contains the sub-directories corresponding to all WPs and tasks; The WP leaders are responsible to deliver the rights on the directory corresponding to their WP, for reading and writing (one of them or both).

Each WP leader has the responsibility to organize the design of adapted SustainSAHEL Templates according to the type of experiment done in each WP. The Templates are Excel files including Data and clear identifiers.

The Research teams have responsibility to complement the SustainSAHEL database with experimental data collected during the SustainSAHEL project. The WP leader has the responsibility to verify that the experimental data are appropriate and deposited correctly and in due time by each partner on the SustainSAHEL experimental database directory.

6. General rules and confidentiality

6.1 Data secrecy and backup

Data management and use is regulated in detail through the Consortium Agreement (CA). The CA regulates the process of obtaining IP protection, exploitation and revenue sharing between partners.

Specific secrecy agreements and/or material transfer agreements will be signed among partners involved in tasks with sensitive IP and commercial issues, if required. Confidentiality for external guests will be managed through secrecy agreements.

6.2 Organisational roles

Parties contributing to connected experiments/surveys will follow a common protocol and provide data in a joint format. These files of raw data will comprise all data necessary for clear identification of experiment ID, experimental design, ownership and any information needed to (meta-)analyse data ex post. The data files are collated in the WP specific collaborative workspace under the supervision of each WP leader. The WP Research Teams will use previous year's data to adjust the protocols for next year's experiments if needed. The timely execution of this annual cycle is important for the WP's functioning.

Researchers of the WP and maybe of other WPs will request data from the database and refine these through statistical analyses to generate results presented in publications. This will typically be an activity near the end of the project, and it is the responsibility of the WP researchers that the collected data will be appropriate for statistical analysis and for scientific publication.

Each WP leader is also in charge of the data flows inside the WP and is responsible for delivering data to other WPs upon request. Those responsible for the WP experiments will use previous year's data to adjust the protocols for the year's experiments as needed. The timely execution of this annual cycle is important for the WPs functioning.

7. Ethical aspects

Ethical issues may arise from the participation of humans in the research. SustainSAHEL, however, will not process any sensitive data (e.g. health data, political views etc.) and the handling of personal data will be done in compliance with the applicable laws, e.g. GDPR and national data protection laws.

8. Conclusion

The Data Management Plan (DMP) of the SustainSAHEL project introduces a detailed data management policy in line with Horizon 2020 open data requirements and guidelines on FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data management.

The FAIR policy defines comprehensible and easy to follow administrative and technical procedures and clear responsibilities for embedding data management activities in the complete project lifecycle. The successful establishment of the SustainSAHEL Collaborative Platform and procedures for data sharing in SustainSAHEL will be a dynamic process and will be implemented and adapted as part of an ongoing process.

9. Literature resources

Data Management in the context of Horizon 2020: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm

Guidelines on Data Management & FAIR data principles under H2020 open-access policy:

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf#page=10

The Open Research Data (ORD) Pilot in H2020: <https://www.openaire.eu>

FAQ: Open Access to Data in Horizon 2020:

https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/newsdocuments/Open_Access_in_H2020.pdf